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Co-author(s):	Philippe Bonnet (UCPH), Alberto Lerner (CF)
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List of Abbreviations

OLAP Online Analytical Processing
OLTP Online Transaction Processing
HDD Hard-Disk Drive
SSD Solid-State Drive
DoA Description of the Action
HPC High-Performance Computing
SIG Special Interest Group
REST Representational State Transfer
DPU Data Processing Unit
LLM Large Language Model

Executive Summary

The CHORYS project aims to demonstrate near-data processing in cloud environments using open, programmable accelerators OpenSSD-V, OpenNIC-V, and a library of data-intensive patterns. This document provides a detailed description of the project's three use cases: the CYSO cloud scenario, a data lake scenario, and an AI scenario. For each case, the report outlines the operational context, system characteristics regarding the developed artifacts, and an initial version of the demonstration scenario to validate the technology in a relevant cloud environment.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope of the Document

The CHORYS project aims to demonstrate near-data processing with open and programmable accelerators in a relevant cloud environment. More specifically, we aim to demonstrate the artifacts developed in the project: OpenSSD-V, OpenNIC-V (whose initial architecture is described in Deliverable D6.1 [1]) and the library of data-intensive patterns (whose host-based component is described in D7.1 [13]). The relevant accelerator-based cloud environment is described in deliverable D9.1 [10].

These demonstrators are based on three use cases identified in the Description of the Action (DoA): (1) a CYSO cloud scenario, (2) a data lake scenario, and (3) an AI scenario. The purpose of this document is to provide a first detailed description of these three use cases. For each use case, we describe (a) the context, (b) the characteristics of the system with a particular focus on the role of the artifacts developed in the project, and (c) the initial version of the demonstration scenario.

Beyond these three use cases, that are the basis for the CHORYS demonstrators, we are exploring the use of open and programmable accelerators in other contexts, including cloud-native Online Transaction Processing (OLTP) and scientific applications. We have established contacts with Tigerbeetle¹, CedarDB² as well as the ERC PoC project CloudStore³ led by Viktor Leis to explore accelerated OLTP. For scientific applications and High-Performance Computing (HPC), we are engaging with the RISC-V International HPC Special Interest Group (SIG)⁴.

1.2 Structure of the Document

We dedicate a section to each use case. We use the same structure for the three use case descriptions with subsections focused on context, system and scenario.

We conclude this deliverable with a discussion of replicability. Indeed, one of the insights of the EU commission meeting on the *AI Continuum: Beyond now*, organized on September 19th 2025 in Brussels was the wide interest in comparing use cases across related Horizon Europe projects. We outline the requirements that replicability imposes on the description of the demonstrators in future deliverables.

¹<https://tigerbeetle.com>

²<https://cedar.db.com>

³<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=lhirqWCg03g>

⁴<https://riscv.org/industries/risc-v-hpc/>

2 Cyso Cloud Use Case

Cyso provides both a public cloud service⁵ and managed hosting solutions⁶. Customers of these solutions have different profiles and requirements. Customers of managed hosting solutions operate bespoke solutions (e.g., a financial system) with own hardware and software components and specific requirements in terms of availability or performance. They are likely to consider a vertically integrated solution that incorporate accelerated hardware, including programmable NICs and SSDs, if it provides end-to-end benefits in terms of cost or performance.

By contrast, Cyso's cloud customers are interested in managed services and cost-effective, high-level abstractions. They are not interested in and may not have the skills to leverage specialized hardware. In the context of Cyso cloud, open and programmable accelerators will be leveraged by Cyso to minimize their cost and increase the scale of their operation in a cost-effective way. More specifically, the Cyso Cloud use case focuses on the impact of open and programmable accelerators on the Cyso cloud object storage solution⁷.

2.1 Context

The Cyso Cloud Object Storage solution provides scalable and reliable storage for cloud customer's data. Built on Ceph, it is S3⁸-compatible and based on NVMe Solid-State Drive (SSD)s.

With their flat structure, scalability, and cost-effectiveness, cloud object stores are the storage component of choice for cloud-native data-intensive systems. Object stores are ideal for storage disaggregation architectures, where the object store manages persistent data, while compute nodes are stateless. Back in 2008, Brantner et al. discussed the feasibility of database systems based on cloud object stores [2]. Ten years ago, the original version of Snowflake used a cloud object store for table data and query results [4] and AWS Aurora relied on a cloud object store for log archival [18]. Today, modern data-intensive systems tend to blend features from analytical and transactional systems [15, 22], but they all rely on cloud object stores.

Object stores are characterized by low storage cost, where the metric is €/GB. There is increasing focus on the performance of object stores. As network performance increases, techniques have been developed to leverage the throughput they provide [5]. Also, caches are often introduced to hide the object store latency (e.g., Clickhouse cache atop S3 [16]).

2.2 System

Using the nomenclature from the Architecture deliverable (D2.4 [9]), Cyso cloud object storage is an external service, built atop an internal service: the Ceph object store⁹, illustrated in Figure 1. The use case focuses on the internal service as this integrates with CHORYS near-data processing devices and forms the base of the external service.

The Ceph object store is composed of two components:

⁵<https://cyso.cloud>

⁶<https://cyso.com>

⁷<https://cyso.cloud/docs/object-storage/>

⁸compatible The Amazon Web Services S3 object store is the reference cloud object store. Launched in 2006 [20], S3 is an object storage service with an HTTP REST API (e.g., put object / get object) [19, 21].

⁹<https://ceph.io/en/discover/technology/>

Use cases

Figure 1: System architecture for the Ceph Object store.

- **RADOS Gateway (RGW)**¹⁰: This component provides a REST API¹¹ that is compatible with the Amazon S3 API¹². It enables clients to manage objects and their containers (called buckets). Each of these objects is an immutable key-value pair with a version id and associated metadata. Note that large files uploaded to the RGW are split into 4MB objects (called tail objects).
- **Object Storage Daemon (OSD) Nodes**: This component manages data on local storage with redundancy and provides access to that data over the network. Multiple OSDs are organized in storage pools (a hashing method is used to map each object to its storage pool, based on globally replicated cluster meta-data). In each storage pool, a primary OSD performs erasure coding to define data chunks and parity chunks for the object. These chunks are striped over the storage pool (the default strip size is 4KB). Note that the objects stored in the OSD can be updated. In typical installations, there is one OSD per disk, i.e., multiple OSDs per storage server.

Currently, OSDs rely on the Bluestore storage back-end to store data on Hard-Disk Drive (HDD) or SSD¹³. The next generation of OSD, named Crimson¹⁴ is optimized for fast storage. It will rely on a new storage back-end, called SeaStore [7, 6]. Seastore is in active development. It is not open-source yet. The list of open issues for Seastore include hardware offloading and optimizations to manage write amplification.

As mentioned earlier, caching is an important technique for cloud object stores. In Ceph object store, caching is implemented at both the RGW layer and the OSD layer. Within the RGW layer, there are two levels of cache: (i) a data cache, named D3N¹⁵, that relies on NVMe SSDs directly attached to the RGW node to store recently used tail objects, and (b) a metadata cache that maintains bucket metadata, user info, and access control information to avoid looking them up in the OSDs for every request¹⁶. Within the OSD layer, Bluestore manages its own caching atop HDD and SSD. In addition, Ceph considers cache tiering¹⁷, as a means to associate

¹⁰<https://docs.ceph.com/en/latest/radosgw/s3/>

¹¹A collection of functions, accessed via HTTP requests and responses, that conforms to the Representational State Transfer (REST) principles: requests identify resources, stateless server, cacheable responses).

¹²<https://docs.aws.amazon.com/AmazonS3/latest/API/Welcome.html>

¹³There exists a legacy storage backend named FileStore.

¹⁴<https://ceph.io/en/news/crimson/>. Crimson has not yet been released for production.

¹⁵https://docs.ceph.com/en/latest/radosgw/d3n_datacache/

¹⁶Note that this cache can be disabled and its size can be configured through the `rgw_cache` parameters. See <https://docs.ceph.com/en/latest/radosgw/config-ref/>.

¹⁷<https://docs.ceph.com/en/latest/rados/operations/cache-tiering/>

a cache pool to a storage pool. However, this feature has been deprecated and the Ceph documentation strongly advises against deploying cache tiers. The rationale is twofolds. First, prefetching, i.e., choosing which objects to promote from storage to cache, is difficult in case locality is hard to identify. Second, the cost associated with data prefetching data might not be offset by the benefits due to cache hits.

Recent research considers offloading the OSD onto a Data Processing Unit (DPU), accessed by the RGW nodes through the network, while the storage back-end remains on the host [12]. This work is interesting because it illustrates that Ceph can be (and should be) redesigned on accelerator-based platforms. In our use case, we propose to explore how OpenNIC-V can be used to accelerate the D3N cache, and how OpenSSD-V can be used to support cache tiering and Seastore acceleration.

2.3 Scenario

The demonstration scenario relies on sanitized traces of read and write requests from Cyso cloud.

The demonstrator system is composed of a rack server, equipped with OpenNIC-V and multiple OpenSSD-V disks. The server runs a RGW and multiple OSD components (we will consider various ratios of OSD per OpenSSD-V device). For the purpose of this demonstrator, OpenSSD-V should be programmed to efficiently support the storage backend (e.g., by minimizing write amplification or providing hardware accelerated functions) or to support efficient cache tiering (e.g., loading data together with the associated metadata, prefetching based on the type of value, prefetching based on D3N access patterns), while OpenNIC-V should be programmed to accelerate D3N cache accesses.

3 Data Lake Use Case

Originally, the term data lake denoted a repository of raw data, structured or unstructured. Parquet was introduced as an open, binary file format for such systems. Today, different types of systems extend data lakes, including data lakehouse and data lakebase, but still rely on data stored in parquet files. We use **data lake** to denote data-intensive systems that rely on Parquet data.

3.1 Context

Open storage format were designed to make it efficient to support analytics based on data stored in a data lake. In particular, Parquet¹⁸ gained traction due to its columnar representation and support for compression, and thanks to the in-memory format, Arrow¹⁹, defined to represent data being read or written to Parquet files²⁰.

Today, different types of systemsAnother class of system merges transactional and analytics capabilities over data stored with an open storage format [22]. Those classes of systems are denoted data lakehouse and data lakebase respectively. extend data lakes. A class of system provides analytics over parquet data. These systems have been designed to support analytical queries, machine learning capabilities and stream processing over an open storage format that extends parquet with additional meta-data to support versioning, transactions or schema evolution (e.g., DeltaLake, Iceberg). Our use case focuses on data processing over parquet.

Figure 2: Parquet format.

Figure 2 illustrates the Parquet file format²¹. While a complete description of the Parquet format and of the requirements It is worth noting that parquet files are immutable. They are written once and read many times. The file meta-data is written at the end of the file,

Many libraries make it easy to read and write to Parquet files from popular programming languages, and in particular Python. However, integrating Parquet files into data processing raises a number of issues identified by Rey et al. [14]: (i) existing column indices and page offsets are optional or too limited due to the interplay with compression techniques, (ii) statistics about data distribution are optional, (iii) efficiently accessing parquet files requires non-trivial logic.

Apache has defined a means to define transformations of data obtained from parquet, based on relational operations. The relational algebra contains operations that take zero or more input datasets and transform them into zero or more output datasets. Substrait defines a core set of

¹⁸<https://parquet.apache.org>

¹⁹<https://arrow.apache.org>

²⁰<https://arrow.apache.org/docs/python/parquet.html>

²¹<https://github.com/apache/parquet-format>

transformations, with an Arrow-based memory representation, and make it possible for users to extend them with their own specialized operations. We consider Substrait for our data-intensive patterns library (see D7.1 [13]).

3.2 System

We consider a working node in a cloud native Online Analytical Processing (OLAP) system, running a column store in memory (i.e., applying transformations on data in columnar format in memory) and equipped with direct attached SSDs [15].

We consider that the local SSD is a version of OpenSSD-V, programmed as a Parquet SSD, i.e., exposing an interface that can ingest parquet files and make it easy to incorporate Parquet data into data processing. This interface abstracts the way data is stored on the storage media and supports efficient integration with the host-based library of data-intensive patterns. Hardware accelerated suboperators are incorporated with this Parquet SSD.

3.3 Scenario

The demonstration scenario relies on analytics queries performed on a parquet dataset defined for a data challenge (e.g., EUROCONTROL PRC 2024 Data Challenge on Aircraft Take-off Weight Estimation²²). The demonstrator system is composed of a rack server, equipped with We consider a single node OLAP benchmark run on parquet data stored in the Parquet SSD.

²²DOI: [10.4121/8cb8484b-dbe7-4750-8b87-a5b1dbc621b4](https://doi.org/10.4121/8cb8484b-dbe7-4750-8b87-a5b1dbc621b4)

4 Accelerated AI inference Use Case

This use case explores how a GPU running a Large Language Model (LLM) can be paired with an OpenSSD-V device to overcome one of the most fundamental limitations of modern inference: the size of GPU memory available to store the model's context.

4.1 Context

Transformers, the architectural foundation of LLM [17], rely on retaining the results of past computations in order to accelerate inference. These retained results form what is known as the Key–Value (KV) cache. The size of this cache directly determines how much context—text or code—the model can consider while running on a given GPU. When the available KV cache is too small to hold the full interaction history, the quality of the generated output degrades as generation proceeds [8]. At present, running LLMs with very long contexts is largely limited to a small number of hyperscalers that design and deploy their own large-scale inference hardware. For most developers, increasing context length today requires slowing down inference significantly or distributing execution across multiple GPUs, both of which are costly and inefficient options.

A key observation is that the KV cache is not uniformly used throughout the entire inference process. Instead, it is structured as a collection of matrix pairs, each of which is accessed only by a specific layer of the model. This insight is based on a preliminary study, which is beyond the scope of this document but will be part of the demonstrator deliverable. This characteristic creates an opportunity to decouple the total KV cache size from the physical memory limits of the GPU by relying on a programmable SSD, such as OpenSSD-V (more detail on how OpenSSD-V should be programmed to support this use case in Section 4.3 below).

In practical terms, this approach enables developers to run significantly more capable local applications, such as advanced code assistants, on a single GPU. Beyond convenience, the implications are important for both security and efficiency. From a security standpoint, sensitive data no longer needs to be transmitted to external cloud services, since inference can be performed locally. From an efficiency standpoint, the GPU can sustain longer, more productive inference sessions without an increase in energy consumption, effectively behaving as though it were equipped with much larger memory.

4.2 System

At a high level, the proposed system is illustrated in Figure 3. It shows a rack server hosting a conventional CPU, a GPU used for inference, and an accelerated SSD placed on the data path between system memory and the inference hardware. Unlike conventional SSDs, the OpenSSD-V integrates programmable RISC-V cores and specialized data-movement hardware, enabling it to actively participate in the execution of the application rather than serving as a passive storage device.

In the proposed use case, a GPU is paired with an OpenSSD-V device that runs a custom program capable of paging portions of the KV cache in and out of GPU memory as they become necessary. By offloading inactive KV cache segments to the OpenSSD-V, a substantial fraction of GPU memory is freed, potentially enabling an LLM to operate with context lengths that are otherwise unattainable on a single device.

Figure 3: System architecture for the accelerated AI inference use case.

Conventional SSDs expose a fixed command interface, typically based on the NVMe standard, which supports immediate read and write operations. While this interface is sufficient for general-purpose storage, it is inadequate for the kind of tightly coordinated, time-critical data movement required by KV-cache paging during LLM inference. The OpenSSD-V overcomes this limitation by allowing custom programs to run directly on the device, and by allowing those programs to define and expose new, application-specific command sets tailored to the needs of the workload.

At the start of LLM inference, once the initial prompt has been processed and the KV caches have been populated for all layers, the GPU transfers to the OpenSSD-V the memory addresses corresponding to each layer's KV-cache region. Along with these addresses, it also provides a static execution map that specifies which KV-cache segment is associated with which layer in the model. This information effectively describes the entire data-access schedule that will be repeated for every decoding step.

With this setup complete, the OpenSSD-V no longer operates as a passive device reacting to individual read or write requests. Instead, it follows a pre-declared, application-driven execution plan. During inference, the GPU proceeds layer by layer through the network and emits a lightweight synchronization signal—a doorbell—each time it enters a new layer. Upon receiving the signal for layer i , the OpenSSD-V immediately performs two coordinated actions: it pages into GPU memory the KV cache required by layer $i+1$, and it pages out the KV cache of layer $i-1$, which is no longer needed.

All data transfers occur through a direct data path into GPU memory using GPU Direct-style mechanisms. This avoids staging data through host memory and avoids involving the CPU in the critical path. As a result, KV-cache movement is overlapped with GPU computation with minimal control-plane overhead.

This execution model fundamentally shifts responsibility for KV-cache management away from the host software stack and onto the storage accelerator itself. From the GPU's perspective, execution remains unchanged: it continues to process layers sequentially and issues only simple synchronization events. From the OpenSSD-V's perspective, inference becomes a continuous streaming workload with a predictable access pattern. Logically, the KV cache appears as a single coherent structure to the LLM, even though it is physically distributed between GPU memory and the accelerator.

4.3 Scenario

The demonstrator scenario relies on data set and model for code generation available at Hugging Face²³.

The demonstrator system is composed of a rack server, equipped with OpenSSD-V. For the purpose of this demonstrator, three programming capabilities are therefore required: OpenSSD-V must support persistent execution contexts in which per-layer KV-cache mappings and schedules can be stored. It must support event-driven execution triggered by GPU doorbells. Finally, it must support sustained, low-latency transfers directly into GPU memory. Together, these capabilities allow the KV-cache paging mechanism to operate transparently and at full inference speed.

²³<https://huggingface.co>

5 Conclusions

This document presented the initial version of the use cases on which the CHORYS demonstrators will be based. For each use case, we described the context, we detailed the systems requirements and we outlined the demonstration scenario.

The use cases are defined bottom-up to illustrate how the artifacts defined in the project address a range of applications that are relevant in the context of a cloud stack, based on European processor technology.

It should be possible to compare the CHORYS use cases to those of comparable EU projects. It should also be possible to replicate the insights gained from the demonstrators in other relevant cloud environments. In a word, it should be possible for other groups to replicate the studies we conduct with our demonstrators.

The US national academies dedicated a chapter to replicability in its exploration of reproducibility and replication in science [11]. The main insight is that replicability is important and hard to achieve. There are is no silver bullet. To be replicable, a study must describe the experimental framework in details (i.e., system under test, workload, metrics and experiments) and the methods used to analyze the experimental data. An idea that might be worth exploring further is to rely on preregistration, also called registered reports [3] (and supported for instance by the Center for Open Science²⁴). While we do not propose registered reports as a form of publication, it might be relevant and interesting to share registered report with other comparable EU projects as a form of peer review for our demonstrators and as a means to ensure that our studies are as replicable as possible.

²⁴<https://www.cos.io/initiatives/registered-reports>

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Consortium

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